

HARNESSING MOBILITY DATA IN CITIES: A CASE STUDY FROM THE BERGEN REGION

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Abstract: *Smart cities attempt to use big data, machine learning, and other topical information and communication techniques (ICTs) to improve energy-consumption, mobility, waste management, and other crucial city functions. Many international pilot projects have been reported in the literature, but data-driven activity in Norway has so far been less extensive. This paper reports on a pre-study that focusses on mobility-related data sources and information needs in the Bergen region. We have identified central actors and their available data, discussed opportunities and challenges with central stakeholders, developed a taxonomy of data types, and reviewed available ontologies for data integration. We are currently exploring a big-data architecture for harvesting, integrating, and making open mobility data more ready for use through a single-entry point.*

INTRODUCTION

Smart City is a term and a practice adopted by a variety of governments, local authorities and international bodies all over the world and is often used as a tool for economic growth and global presence for an actor or organization that adopts it (Caprotti & Cowley, 2016). According to (Caragliu, Del Bo, & Nijkamp, 2011), a city is smart “when investments in human and social capital and traditional (transport) and modern (ICT) communication infrastructure fuel sustainable economic growth and a high quality of life, with a wise management of natural resources, through participatory governance.” Other definitions also highlight a Smart City as having a better integration of information technology with the organisation of a city, participation of its citizens, and other civic stakeholders (Gil-Garcia, Pardo, & Nam, 2015; Goldsmith & Crawford, 2014; Nam & Pardo, 2011). Smart city services can then also be understood as a deep collaboration of citizens and technology (Ahlers, Driscoll, Löfström, Krogstie, & Wyckmans, 2016).

In recent years, many researchers have focussed on providing the ICT infrastructure, analysis power, and services required to fulfill this vision, as we will review in the the following section. Topical themes include ubiquitous computing, the Internet/Cloud of Things (IoT/ClouT), open data, social media, big data analytics, and machine learning/AI. Common goals are improving energy-consumption, mobility, waste management, and other crucial city functions. In this paper, our focus is on mobility in a wide sense. Although many pilot projects have been reported in the international literature, Norwegian data-driven examples described in the scientific literature have so far been scarce, although many cities have Smart City initiatives and projects¹. In 2017, the Norwegian government has launched the Smarter

¹ For example: <https://www.oslo.kommune.no/english/politics-and-administration/smart-oslo/>; <http://smartcitybergen.no/>; <http://trondheim2030.no/2017/11/16/trondheim-soker-om-a-bli-smart-by/>; <http://triangulum-project.eu/index.php/lighthouse-cities/city-of-stavanger-norway/>; <http://nyby.bodo.kommune.no/>; <https://www.nordicedge.org/>; <https://smartcities-infosystem.eu/search/node/norway>; <https://www.ntnu.edu/smartcities>; <http://www.innovasjon Norge.no/no/mulighetsomrader/smar-te-samfunn-og-byer/smart-city-programs-and-events/>

Transport in Norway challenge which aims to develop new, efficient, and environmentally friendly transport solutions in cities and city regions, and which can hopefully stimulate further initiatives.

Mobility data has been defined as “information about the movement of objects, which includes, at least, location and time information” (Pelekis & Theodoridis, 2014), to which we add a prescriptive dimension: *mobility data are data that are about or that can inform the movement of people and objects related to transport*. A particular type of mobility data are *movement data, which are time- and location-stamped data that describe a moving person or object*. Other types of mobility data such as timetables, maps, and information about places add context to the movement data (*mobility-context data*). In a city, public data combined with data produced by citizens and private businesses offers new prospects. Understanding the *urban data potential* is therefore a key challenge in the field of transportation and mobility. The Ubiquitous Data-Driven Urban Mobility (UbiMob) project has worked towards a vision for harnessing such data. The project has outlined an adaptive and context sensitive mobility solution which can, on the one hand, help citizens to make smart decisions while taking their personal need into account and, on the other hand, help service providers and operators to reach equilibrium of mobility services, supply and demand, by smarter resource planning and matchmaking. UbiMob investigated opportunities and challenges around the three biggest Norwegian cities, of which this paper will focus on the Bergen region. Our research goal for the Bergen investigation has been: *to gain an overview of the sources of and needs for mobility-related information in the Bergen area and, thereby, to understand how the generic smart-city concept can best be instantiated in a Bergen context (and perhaps transferred to other Norwegian cities)*. In addition, our research has a practical motivation; we want: *to deepen and widen our competence in topical techniques and tools for big-data analytics, building up a big database of mobility data that can be used for research and teaching*.

The rest of the paper will present the results of our study so far. We will present: examples of existing work, central generators and owners of mobility data in the Bergen region; central information users and example user stories; a taxonomy of mobility information types and their properties; information integration challenges; and preliminary work on a running architecture for mobility data. The conclusion will also outline a few possible paths for further work.

EXISTING WORK

MK:smart² has aimed to collect all sorts of data relevant to the city of Milton Keynes, England, in order to deliver smart city technologies that can support sustainable economic growth. As of April 2018, their data hub has 255 data sets covering topics like transport, energy, water, business, public services information, education, etc. The project has initiated a wide range of research into smart city areas, like how to apply semantic technologies to ensure exploitability of the data hub (d’Aquin, Davies, & Motta, 2015; Daga, d’Aquin, Adamou, & Motta, 2016), how to enable citizens to apply smart city data for their own purposes (Wolff, Gooch, Cavero Montaner, Rashid, & Kortuem, 2017), knowledge discovery (Tiddi, d’Aquin, & Motta, 2015), and handling of energy consumption in smart cities (Cavero, Kortuem, & Foell, 2015). Also in MK:Smart one has collected mobility data and discussed how they can be used to improve public transport (Potter, Valdez, Cook, & Langendahl, 2015), combining smart sensors and user provided data (Valdez, Cook, Langendahl, Roby, & Potter, 2018; Valdez Juarez, Cook, Potter, & Langendahl, 2015). (Daga, d’Aquin, & Motta, 2017) have investigated how data policies propagate through smart city infrastructures where different data with different licenses are constantly being combined, processed, and redistributed in complex and dynamic ways.

(Pellicer et al., 2013) summarized the various smart mobility works or projects worldwide under different smart city areas: smart governance, smart mobility, smart environment, and smart living. The cities and the smart mobility projects that they have investigated are listed as follows: Malaga (automated meter reading, electric vehicles and charging stations, energy efficiency for public facilities, smart grid, etc.),

² <http://www.mksmart.org/>

Paris (electric charging stations, bicycles, exchange plans), Amsterdam (e-citizen participation, electric vehicle and charging stations, energy efficient transport, etc.), Vienna (smart grid, CO₂ emissions reduction), Toronto (efficient metropolitan urban mobility, green mobility policy), New York (open government - open data, improving public transportation, ICT-enabled services and pedestrian spaces for citizens, start-up development for social web), Copenhagen (efficient public transport, natural resources optimization and waste management, energy efficiency), Hong Kong (online services for citizens, RFID in airports, smart cards), Barcelona (project iCity-APP to serve, electric vehicle, urban traffic management, efficient transport, smart homes), Stockholm (waste management system), London (online portal, smart card, networked public service, undergrounds optimization and management, Wi-Fi for metropolitan areas), Rio De Janeiro (traffic management, security system, smart emergency systems), and Vancouver (electric vehicles, green transport). (Yin et al., 2015) conducted a survey on smart cities, and extensively reviewed existing literatures on smart city definitions to come up with a taxonomy from four different perspectives: technical infrastructure, application domain, system integration, and data processing.

The European Initiative on Smart Cities³ aims to support cities and regions in taking ambitious measures to make certain progress by 2020 towards a 40% reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through sustainable use and production of energy. Similarly, the European Innovation Partnership on Smart Cities and Communities⁴ (EIP-SCC) intends to develop collaborative and participatory approaches for cities, industry and citizens to improve urban life through sustainable solutions that include a more efficient use of the energy, transport and Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). There are already several European projects that have their focus in the sectors “Energy”, “Transport & Mobility” or “ICT” that resulted from this European Partnership⁵. Moreover, an abundant set of dynamic, open context-aware, ubiquitous data-driven, ITS (Intelligent Transport System) services can be seen a key step towards a “Smart World”—an integration of smart environments to better understand our neighbourhood so as to improve our well-being. Such services include adaptive personalised maps (Liang, Poslad, & Meng, 2008), adaptive vehicle navigation (Meng & Poslad, 2009), smart fleet management and traffic monitoring (Giacobbe, Puliafito, & Villari, 2010), road incident detection (Chatzigiannakis, Grammatikou, & Papavassiliou, 2007), congestion avoidance (Parrado & Donoso, 2015), speed control via smart interaction with roadside controls (Pérez et al., 2010), context-based vehicle maintenance (Matsuzaki & Todoroki, 2008), car parking aids (Ji, Ganchev, O’Droma, Zhao, & Zhang, 2014), human driver monitoring (Sahayadhas, Sundaraj, & Murugappan, 2012) and better driving safety (Jang, Kim, & Cho, 2011).

SOURCES OF MOBILITY DATA

There are four major urban mobility data stakeholders:

1. Public actors (such as central governments, cities, municipalities, urban communities, etc);
2. Businesses (whether they are public service concession holders or not), including start-ups;
3. End-users (citizens, tourists);
4. Social networks and virtual communities.

In order to gain an overview of the generators and owners of mobility data in the Bergen region, we have communicated face-to-face, by phone, and by email with more than 20 different stakeholders and additionally reviewed numerous documents, web sites and APIs, which we divide broadly into: government, ideal organisations, and business/commerce. Citizen-generated and open data constitute additional categories that we will address.

3 <https://setis.ec.europa.eu/set-plan-implementation/technology-roadmaps/european-initiative-smart-cities>

4 <http://ec.europa.eu/eip/smartcities/>

5 <https://eu-smartcities.eu/>

Government

Several units inside Bergen City (Bergen kommune) collect and maintain mobility data. The Department of City Development's Section for City Environment (Bymiljøetaten) has the main responsibility for mobility, including city roads, street parking, e-car loading spots, and bike lanes, about which they collect and maintain data. The Parkering i Bergen app manages street-parking payments. Public parking garages are run by a semi-private entity (Bergen parkering) that runs automatic number-plate registration (ANPR) as part of one of their payment systems. Information about available parking slots – including e-car loading stations – are made available online and through a REST API. The payment app is maintained by a daughter company, SesamSesam. The section also administers the city bikes, which has so far been operated by Urban Infrastructure Planner (UIP, see below). In addition, they managed the city's car-toll stations, operated by BT Signaal (below).

Other city departments also have sections that work with mobility data. The Climate Section operates four air measurement stations and sometimes, but not regularly, order surveys about perceived city climate. The Section for Digitalisation and Innovation is developing a data lake of open data, which they anticipate will include mobility-data in the near future. The Section for Safety and Preparedness ("beredskap") has access in principle to a wide variety of mobility-related information sources, including positioning data from mobile phones, but cannot use or share them for privacy reasons. Their responsibilities include acting as a hub for sharing emergency- and response-relevant information among governmental, ideal, and commercial organisations, much of which is mobility-related. The Section for Information is a distributor of many information types but does not maintain mobility-related data of its own. Bergen City Event maintains a web site of public events like concerts.

On the regional (Hordaland county) level, Skyss manages collective transport by buss, metro, speed boat, and ferry. It maintains schedules and runs automatic passenger counting (APC) systems on around half the buses in the county. GPS coordinates are collected and maintained by a subcontractor, xxx. Boats and ferries are operated by private companies we will return to later.

On the national level, The Norwegian Public Roads Administration (Statens vegvesen) continually collects traffic data from all of Norway using a variety of methods, including digital images, much of which is made openly available in Datex II, an XML-format for communicating and exchanging traffic information standard.⁶ EnTur is a daughter company that runs and owns the sales and ticketing system for the national railways (NSB), whereas BaneNor is a government agency that collects and maintains information about the railway network and its traffic, which they make available through an open REST API and web site. Avinor is a state-owned limited company that operates most of Norway's civil airports, among them Bergen Airport Flesland, making information about arrivals and departures available through open REST APIs and on the web.

Norwegian maps are maintained by Statens kartverk and are often for pay, but there are open alternatives. Weather services are provided by met.no through a web site and an open REST API.

Commercial enterprises

On the regional level, taxi companies such as Bergen taxi, alongside nationwide competitors Norgestaxi and Taxi 1, routinely collect data about taxi positions at stops. For each ride, start and stop zones, times, and travel distance are collected.

Urban Infrastructure Planner (UIO) has operated the city-bike trials in Bergen and has bid for a longer-term contract. They maintain an app and an API that provides an overview of available city bikes and return slots in their stations. They provide open data sets of usage statistics including rental and return positions and times. BT Signaal operates the ring of toll stations around Bergen that collects data about

⁶ CEN TS 16157: DATEX II – The standard for ITS on European Roads, http://www.datex2.eu/sites/www.datex2.eu/files/Datex_Brochure_2011.pdf

numbers and categories of passing vehicles by the minute, but do not share it. Private parking garages run similar systems to Bergen parkering.

Regional operating companies for speed boats and ferries collect information about past, current, and anticipated future passenger counts (by route and stop in the case of busses), as well as vehicle positions, time tables and actual departure and arrival times. On the national level, long-distance air-traffic, bus, and ferry companies collect similar information.

National and international mobile phone companies keep continuous track of mobile devices, identifiable through the identities both of devices (IMEIs) and subscribers (IMSI). Increasingly, such devices go beyond mobile phones to a wider range of more or less smart, mobile-networked things. However, privacy laws strictly limit their ability share such information – and to use it themselves. UMS (Unified Messaging Systems) offers location-based citizen messaging in emergency situations, a service to which municipalities in the Bergen area have access. Internet providers can also collect similar, but less frequent and less precise, data when laptops and other mobile equipment move between network access points.

In contrast, international ICT companies like Google may know more about mobility in Bergen and in Norway than any local or national actor. In particular, Google, Apple and Microsoft harvest personal mobility data through their mobile phone operating systems, which they leverage to augment their map services with services such as travel-time estimates depending on time and day. Only little of that data is available to local actors.

Ideal organisations

The Bergen car pool (Bildeleringen), with more than 1800 household members, owns several hundred cars in more than 90 locations in the Bergen city area. Online Convadis terminals in each car keep track of use and location when parked, but GPS data are not collected when a car is in use. The online car-booking system *Let's Go*. A subcontractor manages member accounts and generates car-usage statistics on demand.

Citizen-generated data

Through their mobile phones and other gadgets (smart watches, exercise wristbands, etc.), electronic payment transactions, social media use (which may be geotagged or contain mobility-related information), networked cars and other vehicles, most citizens leave continuous data trails as they go about with their daily lives. Coined *sousveillance*⁷ (Kitchin, 2014) this army of “little brothers” also generates and maintains enormous amounts of mobility-related data, which are not in general openly available (as citizens tend to give away ownership of their data to the app and service providers in return for access to free services). Some of this data are directly or indirectly collated by behemoths like Amazon, Apple, Facebook, Google/Alphabet, and Microsoft⁸, the rest ends up with a large number of small- and medium-sized app and social-media providers. A few of them, like Twitter, at least for now share their data within limits. Most of them, like Facebook and Google, do not share the data itself, although they do provide free services based on it. Although, the new European Data Directive and Regulation will return some of the control over such data back to the originating person, it will work only on an individual-by-individual basis. Although mature citizen-centric/user-owned open alternatives exist (such as GNU social as an alternative to Twitter and Diaspora to Facebook), they are not yet widely used.

⁷ Norw.: “undervåkning”.

⁸ In an international context, at least Alibaba, Baido, and Tencent should also be added to this list.

Open data

Although most of it has originated from governments and their citizens, open data have particular characteristics that make them worth to discuss of their own. data.norge.no is the national portal and web hotel for open data sets. It currently contains around 1100 data sets, but only 60 of them are transport related and none of those are specific to the Bergen region. GeoNames.org and OpenStreetMap are crowdsourced data sets about geography and transport networks, which are important types of mobile context data. General datasets like Wikipedia can also be used to enrich map and other data. Of course, for many or most of these types of open data sets, there are also (for-pay or restricted) commercial or governmental alternatives that sometimes have higher quality (completeness, correctness, precision, timeliness, etc.), depending on the use case.

Because they use standard formats and vocabularies on the syntactic and semantic levels, semantic open data sets (or knowledge graphs) using technologies such as RDF, OWL, and SPARQL are a particularly interesting type of mobility context data. GeoNames provides a simple ontology and several semantic interfaces to its data, whereas LinkedOSM is a semantic version of OpenStreetMap. DBpedia is a semantic extract from Wikipedia, whereas Wikidata is a natively crowdsourced semantic fact database aiming to provide structured facts to Wikipedia projects, making reuse and maintenance easier. Table 1 presents an overview of the most central sources of regional mobility data we have uncovered.

Table 1. Central sources of mobility data in the Bergen region.

Movement of buses, taxis, planes, trains, boats/ferries (by GPS)	Movement of people into and out of buses with automated passenger counting
Passenger counts for buses/planes/trains/boats/ferries	Stops for buses/taxis/trains, quays for boats/ferries
Movement of vehicles, cyclists and walkers through mobility sensors or through toll stations and road counters	Travel/tourism data, including arriving cruise ships, hotel bookings, etc.
Zone maps for boats/taxis/boats/ferries	Weather and pollution data, e.g., about icy roads and air quality
Route information and time tables for buses/trains/places/boats/ferries	Information about events such as concerts, parades, protests, sports, etc.
Maps, including road maps and bike/walking paths, and other geographical data, including points of interest	Information about emergencies such as traffic accidents, fires, etc.
Availability of city bikes and pooled cars (and of return slots for bikes), and other modes of car or bike sharing (e.g. cargo bikes)	Information about other deviations such as temporarily closed roads; police investigations; delayed and suspended buses, planes, trains, boats, ferries; redirected bus/train routes, etc.
Movement of motorised vehicles through tollbooths, into and out of parking/houses spots, e.g., through RFID or ANPR (automated number plate recognition)	Apps (or related web sites) that track personal mobility (fitness apps, and everything location-based or with a location option, including Twitter, Facebook, Instagram etc.)
Movement of city bikes and pooled cars between pick-up points	Apps that track vehicle mobility (parking, city bikes, pooled cars)
Parking spots of various types on the streets and in parking garages	Train/plane/ferry/boat ticketing systems (bus ticketing is today mostly by zone and less useful)
Mobile phone movement (through cell towers, GPS, WiFi connections)	Ticketing systems for events such as cinema, concerts and sports
Open reference data from Wikipedia/DBpedia/Wikidata, OpenStreetMap, GeoNames, etc. about points of interest.	Pick-up points for city bikes and pooled cars
	E-vehicle charging stations
Population and demographics	Survey data about perceived life quality, travel habits, etc.

MOBILITY-DATA USER STORIES

In our communication with central stakeholders, and drawing on our own experience as both city residents and researchers, we have identified opportunities for using mobility data to create a smarter city region. We have formulated each opportunity as a user story to make it as concrete and as well aligned with future development work as possible. Table 2 shows examples of user stories we have identified. In addition, many other uses of mobility-data have been reported in the research literature, e.g., (Benevolo, Dameri, & D’Auria, 2016). Along with the stories we have collected ourselves, they provide a rich starting point for further work on making Bergen and other Norwegian cities smarter.

Table 2. Examples of user stories

As a citizen, I want to find neighbours with similar driving patterns in order to organise car pooling to and from work.	As a taxi company owner, I want to precisely predict demands for taxis in order to lower prices and increase profits.
As a city official, I want to monitor greenhouse gas emissions in order to document the effects of the city’s traffic regulations on the environment.	As a traffic manager, I want to detect and predict the consequences of road accidents in real time in order to proactively redirect traffic around accident sites.
As a city official, I want to understand policy impact on mobility in the city to better plan traffic interventions and change modal split, the types of transport people use to get into or around in the city.	As a collective traffic provider, I want to offer seamless single-ticket trips that may also include city bikes, car pooling, car-sharing vehicles and parking slots in order to make collective travels more convenient for citizens.
As an emergency manager, I want to have a live overview of people’s locations during an emergency in order to direct rescuers and medical personnel.	As a city environment official, I want to understand the interplay between weather, traffic and air pollution in order to keep the city air clean.
As an emergency manager, I want to predict people’s movements after an emergency in order to reduce bottlenecks and better support evacuation.	As a first responder, I want to know the quickest travel path to a place of emergency, taking into account the resulting traffic congestion, in order to help citizens in need.
As a parking garage manager, I want to offer dynamic pricing in order to make the city center attractive for shoppers and retailers.	As a road manager, I want to monitor and predict the consequences of closing road segments for maintenance in order to avoid congestion / accidents and ensure smooth traffic.

MOBILITY-DATA CHARACTERISTICS

Developing apps and services that realise each of these user stories will in most cases require integration of several different types of mobility data originating from different sources. To prepare for large-scale data integration, we are developing a taxonomy of mobility-data types and characteristics, which may evolve into an ontology of mobility-data types.

Types of mobility data

In the introduction, we defined *mobility data* as *data that are about or that can inform the movement of people and objects*. We proceeded to distinguish between *movement data* and *mobility-context data*. Movement data are *data that describe how a person or object moves by time- and location-stamps*. Hence, we have reserved the term movement data for data that are both temporally and spatially located, even on a coarse/aggregate level. By live *movement data* we have meant more frequently updated (many times an hour) and spatially fine-grained (at least to street level) movement data. Mobility-context data are other types of mobility data - such as timetables, maps, and information about places – that add context to the movement data.

Specific characteristics of mobility data

With these subtypes of mobility data in mind, we go on to investigate their detailed characteristics and how they differ on the conceptual level:

- *Temporality*: whether the data describe phenomena that change with time, if so, the period the data cover, the delay from the mobility event until the data are available and the frequency of updates, with ranges from milliseconds to a year or longer for statistical reports (temporal granularity).
- *Spatiality*: whether the data are spatially located and, if so, the area the data covers and the spatial precision of the data (spatial granularity).
- *Subject*: whether the data are about, e.g., individuals, vehicles, places, structures (such as buildings), events, weather conditions, etc., or about relations between two or more such phenomena.
- *Sensitivity*: for data about individuals, whether the person is alive and can be directly or indirectly identified through the data (i.e., personal data) and, if so, whether the personal data are also sensitive (e.g., about race, religion, health, political activities, criminal matters, or sex life.)

We consider all of these data types mobility data because they are about and can inform the movement of people and objects.

General characteristics

Of course, all the general properties of data such as availability, ownership, and provenance apply to mobility data as well. Also, mobility data are available in different formats, publicly or not, through file downloads or web APIs. Size and bandwidth are particular concerns, i.e, how large are the data and how much do they grow by the day or hour. For example, meteorological or socially generated data, if harvested unselectively, can quickly grow prohibitively large.

Other mobility ontologies

There are several other mobility-related ontology building efforts. Datex II is a widely used XML-based format that has been “developed to provide a standardised way of communicating and exchanging traffic information between traffic centres, service providers, traffic operators and media partners”. Datex II is experimentally available as an OWL ontology, Linked Datex II. km4city (Bellini, Benigni, Billero, Nesi, & Rauch, 2014, p. 4) is a natively semantic vocabulary for interoperating the very large numbers of public and private mobility data sets that are available from local governments and other sources, partitioned into administration, street guides, points of interest, public transportation, sensors and time. MobiVoc is an ongoing vocabulary initiative that is currently limited to parking-related concepts. This core of dedicated mobility vocabularies are interlinked — or interlinkable — with a large number of surrounding vocabularies for domains such as geodata and maps (e.g., LinkedGeoData), weather (e.g., WeatherOntology), sensors (e.g., Semantic Sensor Network (Compton et al., 2012)) etc. In addition, CityGML is an open standardised data model and exchange format for digital 3D models of cities and landscapes, although it is not yet defined in an ontology.

To the extent they are semantic, these vocabularies build on many of the same general vocabularies for describing general phenomena such as times (e.g., OWL-Time) and locations (geo), people (FOAF, bio), organisations (org), events (the Event Ontology), provenance (PROV-O), and data ownership (CC). The Linked Open Vocabularies site offers an overview of reusable semantic vocabularies on the web (Vandenbussche, Atemezing, Poveda-Villalón, & Vatant, 2017).

However, these mobility-related ontologies (DatexII, km4city, MobiVoc) and format (CityGML) tend to focus on the middle (domain-specific) and lower (context-specific) levels, whereas our taxonomy belongs to the upper (general) level: the subtypes and characteristics we have been identified can be used to describe and systematise types and properties found in middle- and lower-level mobility ontologies and vocabularies.

ARCHITECTURE FOR MOBILITY DATA

We are currently building a historical database of open mobile data from the Bergen region. We want to harvest, integrate, and make open mobility data ready for use through a single entry point for research and education purposes. Our still-evolving architecture is composed to: *harvesters* that download data from web and store then in a *staging area* where they can be *transformed* and *loaded* into a *NoSQL database* which becomes available as input to *big-data analytics* tools, such as Spark (Zaharia et al., 2016). Our focus has so far been on developing scripts for harvesting, transformation, and loading into Cassandra, our chosen wide-column store.

Harvesting

We use simple scripts, mostly written in Python and some Java, to continuously download open mobility data. The data are mostly available through APIs, but also as files and by scraping web pages. So far, we have written harvesters for: Bergen bysykkel (city bikes), Bergen City Events, a selection of local newspapers, met.no, EnTur, Avinor, Tweets with Bergen-related keywords or geotagged around Bergen, and radnett.nrp.no. The harvesters (along with the transformers and loaders) run on a medium-CPU Amazon EC2 Ubuntu Linux cloud server, currently with a 512G disk. The various scripts run as cron jobs with frequencies between every minute and once an hour. While processing load is not yet heavy, the elastic storage volumes offered by EC2 makes it easy to handle growing data volumes.

Staging

The harvesters store the data as JSON files. The files are organised in series, typically store in the same folder in the staging area, and so that each series contain files produced by the same harvester and containing homogeneously-structured JSON objects. Each file is time-stamped and corresponds to a single harvester run. Most harvesters produce only a single JSON file series, but some produce several.

Transformation

Before uploading to the NOSQL database, the JSON files are prepared in several ways. Character set encoding is standardised to plain ASCII and UTF-8 if necessary, and times and dates are reformatted if necessary to the standards used by Cassandra.

File series with a simple structure, i.e., whose JSON objects are regular and not deeply nested, can be uploaded directly into a database table (called column families in Cassandra). However, some harvesters generate more complex file series that must be split up and further simplified before each series can be uploaded into a database table.

For example, every JSON object that represents a tweet also contains a nested object that represents the user who made the tweet. If that user makes 200 tweets in a month without changing their profile, the profile data are repeated 200 times in the JSON file series. We therefore normalise the series by splitting the JSON objects that represent users out into a separate JSON file series (but retaining a `user_id` entry for each tweet). We handle other cases of repeated JSON objects in the same way, although complete normalisation is not an ambition (because Cassandra database optimised for reading).

In a similar way, we also split repeated JSON objects (i.e., JSON arrays) out into separate JSON files. Although Cassandra has some provision for complex and repeated columns, we prefer a simple and flat data structure. We therefore also flatten the structure of our JSON files by using concatenated key names (after arrays/repeated object have been eliminated).

Loading

The transformed JSON file series are uploaded into Cassandra. We attempt to make the loading stage a streamlined as possible by doing as much of the preparation as possible in the transformation stage (where generic tools are available, like JSONPath, an XPath-like tool for JSON). We attempt to transform the harvested file series to a point where even the database tables (or column families) can be suggested. This tool works by reading a selection of (or all) the JSON files in a series. For each JSON key-value pair it encounters, it uses simple heuristics to try to identify the narrowest (most specific) Cassandra type for that value. For each key found in the series, the tool then collects all the Cassandra types that have been used and counts their occurrences so far. Based on this, the tool suggests a suitable Cassandra datatype for each key, which will become a column in the database table.

The user can inspect and perhaps modify the suggested types. The user must also select columns to form the table's key. The tool can then create the database table, load it with initial data, and uploading transformed JSON files as they arrive from the harvesters and transformers. Arriving JSON objects that do not fit the table format – as can happen when data formats change upstream - are not uploaded, but written to a backlog file of JSON objects to be inserted later when the database table has been properly revised.

Storing

New types of distributed database management systems (DDBMS) have been designed to accommodate big-data collections (of tera and petabytes) in a flexible way. Coined NoSQL (Non-SQL) databases, they extend traditional relational and SQL-based data models to focus on scale and to accommodate new types of data and attributes with little effort. We have chosen Cassandra for our project.

Cassandra is one of the most used NoSQL DBMSs, which combines features from key-value pairs and wide-column stores. In addition to flexibility, scalability and read-orientation, Cassandra is designed to support data replication, resilience towards failure, and ease of elastically adding more machines to the database cluster. It is also optimised for retrieving and adding new data as opposed to updating existing data.

Future components

After the feasibility study and data assessment, work on the mobility database is in the initial stages but already shows promising results. Most urgently, we need to build more transformers and improve the generic loader. Currently, only tweets are continuously being loaded into Cassandra. The other file series remain in staging. We are also developing more harvesters, and want to gain access to further data sources that are not yet open, for example by collaborating more closely with the municipality and county as well as industrial actors. On the usage side, we want to use Spark to post-process the data from Cassandra, both to provide simple data services exposed as REST APIs and to extract re-combined data sets that can be used for data analytics. The user stories we have presented in Table 2 are good starting points. Semantic lifting and integration of our data sets is another high priority.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

The paper has presented our work on a pre-study that focusses on mobility-related information sources and needs in the Bergen region. Although this is an area in rapid development, we think we have satisfied our first research goal, which was to get an overview of the sources of and needs for mobility-related information in the Bergen area. In this way, we have also made progress on the second: to understand how the generic Smart City concept can best be instantiated in a Bergen (and thus Norwegian) context, using mobility data as an example. We are also on the way to satisfying our practical ambition with the project:

to get experience with topical techniques and tools for big-data processing and machine learning, by building up a multi-source big data store with potential uses both for research and teaching.

We are continuing the work with the BDEM project, still harnessing mobility data from the Bergen region, but emphasising their uses for emergency situations. This should not preclude the same data being useful also for pure mobility-related analysis. While a lot of data is becoming more and more available through the large search engines, there is a specific need to take local characteristics, information needs, and environments into account. Building up local databases or federated open data stores with analytics capabilities ultimately benefits all citizens and society as a whole by making data more accessible, findable, and integrateable. Quality assurance and processing on top of raw data increases the utility for a number of scenarios. Apart from the use cases developed here, this also includes an easier support for startups, for research, and for citizen science.

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